

SUBEPIFIZAR OSTEOHONDROPATHYA OF THE HUMERUS TROCHLEA (OSTEOCHONDROITIS DISSECANS)**Umarov A.***Radiologist of the highest category, Republican Clinical Hospital No. 1, Republic of Uzbekistan***Rustamova U.***Scientific Secretary and Senior Researcher of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center for traumatology and orthopedics, Republic of Uzbekistan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236917>**Abstract**

On this scientific material, a new type of osteochondropathy in the elbow joint was discovered in adolescents aged 10 to 14 years and long-term changes in the stage of repair over the age of 25 years. The analysis of the data was carried out on the basis of a comparison of etiology and pathogenesis with other varieties of osteochondropathy. Also, the analysis was compared after the specific treatment used for osteochondropathy, which showed good results. Thus, early and correct X-ray diagnostics with an understanding of the clinical picture of osteochondropathy in the elbow joint will lead to early treatment and recovery.

Keywords: osteochondropathy, aseptic necrosis, Koenig-1 disease, Panner-2 disease.

Introduction

Osteochondropathy (OCP) is a common bone disease, both among children, adolescents (teenagers) and young adults, as well as middle-aged (30-40 years) and older (55-65 years). It leads to severe pain and limitation in the joints, although in most cases the process proceeds favorably and is an X-ray finding. It has the same X-ray picture, a chronic benign clinical course and a favorable outcome, with timely identification and early treatment. Synonyms of the disease: osteochondritis, epiphysionecrosis, osteochondrolysis, aseptic necrosis. At present, 4-5 types of OCP are widely known: Legg-Calvé-Perthes disease, Köhler-II disease, Osgood-Schlatter disease, Scheuermann-Mau disease, Schinz-Haglund-1 disease.

Material and methods of research

The basis for publishing this article was the new type of OCP of the humeral trochlea in the elbow joint that we identified. Our analysis of the medical literature shows that not only the new type we identified, but also many other types of OCP are unknown to a large circle of specialists. Therefore, a correctly collected anamnesis, an accurate analysis of X-ray images are of great diagnostic value for establishing the diagnosis: "Osteochondropathy".

During the period 2014-2019 and 2021-2023 (8 years), **414 patients** aged 10 to 14 years old came to us for an X-ray examination due to injury or pain in the elbow joint. All adolescents who were diagnosed with OCP of the humeral trochlea were actively involved in volleyball, badminton, tennis, and judo.

Of the **414 patients**, **128** came on an **outpatient** basis, **286** patients on an **emergency** basis. Some patients underwent analog X-ray images in 2 projections (frontal and lateral) on a stationary X-ray machine EDR-750 (Hungary) 1979: time 0.16 sec, voltage 50 keV, current 200 mA, equivalent dose 0.08 mSv. Other patients underwent digital X-ray images in 2 projections (frontal and lateral) on a stationary X-ray machine "Baccara" (France) 2015: time 0.10 sec, voltage 45 keV, current 200 mA, equivalent dose 0.06 mSv. The

obtained X-ray images **revealed 319** different bone-traumatic injuries in the elbow area, of which (**outpatient in 88 patients, emergency in 231 patients**):

The OCP of the humeral trochlea at different stages was detected in **12 patients (outpatient in 8 patients in Chirchik town, emergency in 4 patients in Mirobad district of Tashkent town of the Republic of Uzbekistan)**.

No bone-traumatic injuries or joint changes were detected in **83 patients (outpatient in 32 patients, emergency in 51 patients)**. This is a *control, healthy group*.

In percentage terms, the OCP in relation to the total number (414 patients) who sought radiographic examination was $2.89 \pm 0.008\%$ or 1: 34.5.

Among the total number of detected injuries (319 patients), the OCP is $3.76 \pm 0.001\%$ or 1: 26.6.

Among the control, healthy group (83 patients), the OHP is $14.45 \pm 0.007\%$ or 1: 6.9.

But the percentage ratio in the control, healthy group should be considered a relative and unreliable indicator, since there is no world practice, including in the Republic of Uzbekistan, for mandatory X-ray examination of the elbow joint for all adolescents (teenagers).

According to foreign data, the frequency of damage to the OCP of the humeral trochlea in the world is 2.2: 100 000 examined elbow joints [46]. We believe that the number of cases of the disease is much higher. The reason is that, as we indicated earlier, the OCP of the humeral trochlea is not known to a large circle of specialists: orthopedists, radiologists, rheumatologists, endocrinologists.

If we take into account that 8 cases of OCP of the humerus trochlea were identified in the Chirchik town of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period from 2014-2021 in the age group of 10-14 years (9604 adolescents (teenagers)). Which is $0.083 \pm 0.0003\%$ or 1: 1200.5.

4 cases of OCP of the humerus trochlea were identified in the Mirobad district of Tashkent town of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period from 2021-2023

in the age group of 10-14 years (8381 adolescents (teenagers)). Which is $0.047 \pm 0.0007\%$ or 1: 2095.25.

By reducing the indicator to the arithmetic mean, we find that the incidence of cases of the disease OCP of the humeral trochlea is on average 1: 1650.

Also, over 8 years (from 2014-2019 and from 2021-2023), we radiologically examined 68 patients aged 20-30 years who came to us with a diagnosis of "elbow osteoarthritis". Of these, the OCP of the humeral trochlea was detected in only one patient aged 28 years, in the terminal stage (reparation) (Fig. 16), which amounted to $1.47 \pm 0.001\%$ or 1: 68.

For the sake of purity of the study, we compared the radiographic picture of the identified new type of OCP of the humeral trochlea with:

1) **König's disease-1.** Surgeon König (Germany) described in 1888 the pathology of the knee joint as a partial (wedge-shaped) osteochondropathy of the articular surface (osteochondritis dissecans).

2) **Panner's disease-2.** Radiologist Panner H.J. (Denmark) described in 1927 the pathology of the elbow joint as aseptic subcartilaginous necrosis of the cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus.

3) **Hegemann's disease.** In 1951, radiologist Hegemann N. (Germany) described the pathology of the elbow joint as osteochondrosis of the humerus trochlea.

In the case of König-1 disease, we compared the anatomical structure of the upper and lower limbs, which are similar in structure. The knee joint is formed by three main bones: femur, tibia, and fibula (not counting the patella, the function of which in the elbow joint is performed by the apophysis (olecranon) fused with the ulna to form the ulnar process). The elbow joint also involves three bones: the humerus, ulna and radius.

1) In **König's disease-1**, the inner intermuscular edge of the epiphysis of the femoral epiphysis trochlea is affected (Fig. 2, 3, 4). In newly diagnosed disease, the inner (medial) epiphysis of the humerus trochlea is also affected. The X-ray picture in König-1 disease in the knee joint is similar to the osteochondropathy we found in the elbow joint and includes all stages of development of this disease with the final formation of a sequestra-like area of necrosis. This focus of necrosis may sometimes separate from the underlying bone and be covered by its own hyaline cartilage, forming a free body - a joint "mouse", sometimes limiting movement in the joint.

2) In **Panner's disease-2** (Fig. 5, 6, 20), the cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is affected in isolation and is flattened and deformed. The articular gap between the cephalic eminence of the humerus and the caput of the radius bones. The pathologic process occurs in the **lateral** side of the elbow joint. A pronounced, persistent external angular deformity in the elbow joint (*cubitus varus*) and limitation of flexion-extension functions in the elbow joint are formed, even after treatment.

That we've identified the pathologic process occurs on the **medial** side of the elbow joint. The articular surface of the humerus trochlea is flattened and deformed. The articular gap is enlarged between the valgus and the humerus trochlea. In the early stages, there appears an external angular deformity (Fig. 6) in the joint. But in the future, when physical loads on the joint are avoided, as well as with timely, correct treatment, 92-95% of the limitation of flexion-extension functions in this joint is not observed. The process of elbow joint recovery is faster and the outcome is more favorable compared to Panner-2 disease.

**(in both figures, the arrow indicates a fragmented area of necrosis - sequestrum)*

König's disease-1
The right knee joints
 (direct projection, comparative images)

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

*(arrow indicates fragmented necrosis area - sequestrum)
 Fig. 3. Deformation of the articular surface of the knee joint of the "fishtail" type.

Panner's disease-2

Fig. 5
 (diagram)

Fig. 6

3) **Hegemann's disease** describes osteoarthritic changes in the humerus associated with sports injury (Fig. 7). Herd Hegemann referred to the disease he identified as osteochondrosis of the humerus trochlea. He made this conclusion based on X-ray images of only 3 patients from 1945 to 1951, considering it a rare disease.

The majority of American, European, and Japanese radiologists and orthopedists from 1951 to 2024 cannot reach a common opinion and consider this disease, like Hegemann, to be *osteochondrosis* (trochleitis) of the humerus [42,45,48,49,50,51,52,55,56,58,60,63,65,66,70,71,75,76,78,86,90]. In their works, they tend to combine Hegemann's disease with a rare deformity of the humeral trochlea of the "fishtail" type. Apparently, Western, European, and Japanese specialists seem inclined

to believe that Hegemann's disease represents a spectrum of vascular disorders of the distal humerus, ranging from benign mild vascular disorder, to complete avascular necrosis after fractures.

In their works, they tend to combine Hegemann's disease with the rare fishtail deformity of the humeral trochlea. Apparently, Western, European and Japanese experts tend to believe that Hegemann's disease is the end stage of osteoarthritis and osteoarthrosis associated with vascular disorders of the distal humerus, ranging from benign mild vascular disorder to complete avascular necrosis after fractures [41,44,46,49,50,52,56,62,65,70,71,75,80,81,83,90]. In their works, they recommend additional imaging to confirm the presence of fishtail deformity, intra-articular loose bodies and signs of osteoarthritis to decide whether surgical treatment is necessary. Since there is

no clear etiology for both diseases and the clinical symptoms and radiographic manifestations are difficult to distinguish, these experts prefer to call both phenomena "vascular disorders of the trochlear growth plate" to avoid confusion in definitions and discussions [42,45,48,49,50,51,52,55,56,58,60,63,65,66,70,71,75,76,78,86,90].

The etiology as well as the optimal treatment of Hegemann disease and fishtail deformity is a subject of ongoing debate. A systematic review of clinical studies of Hegemann's disease and fishtail deformity was conducted to:

- 1) formulate the most current theory on etiology to better define these conditions;
- 2) summarize the most common radiological descriptions on radiographs;
- 3) provide an overview of various treatment options.

As of 2024, a total of 22 articles have been printed in the foreign literature: seven articles on Hegemann's disease, including 8 patients, and 15 articles on fishtail deformity, including 58 patients [90]. In my opinion, this is due to the fact that foreign specialists studied patients mainly in the end (arthritic) stage of the disease, associating the etiology with fractures, with posttraumatic osteoarthritis and arthritis.

We have studied medical articles by foreign authors related to methods of diagnostics and treatment of "osteochondrosis" of the humeral trochlea in the elbow joint. In their studies, they did not take into account that this could be a banal OCP. In our practice, we have seen patients in different stages of osteochondropathy. Understanding all stages of development of this disease, at which OCP can be recognized by characteristic radiological manifestations (symptoms - *osteochondrosis manifesta*), it was not difficult for us to distinguish one stage from another.

Stages of development of Hegemann's disease (osteochondrosis of the humerus trochlea)
[by to Schumacher et al. 1981].

Stage 1: Initial loss of density, later plaque-like sclerosis of the epiphyseal ossification center;

Stage 2: Reduction in size and compaction of the ossification center;

Stage 3: Loosening, accompanied by the beginning of new ossification;

Having analyzed all foreign material, having conducted a retrospective and prospective analysis, we came to the conclusion that the deformation of the distal end of the humerus by the "fishtail" type [53,55,63,70] and osteochondritis dissecans (OD) of the humeral trochlea [42,45,48,49,50,51,53,56,58,60,65,66,71,75,76,78,86,90] are different and independent diseases. Sometimes both diseases can occur together. The cause of the humerus deformity in the elbow joint by the type of "fishtail", as a complication, are fractures of the distal humerus: supracondylar, fracture of the trochlea, lateral or medial condyle, or even after epiphyseal fractures of Salter-Harris type I in childhood, which lead to a central bone deficiency of the distal epiphysis of the humerus, and to the formation of a depression or pit in the trochlea [53,55,63,70].

Osteochondritis dissecans (OD) is a type of OCP in the form of limited necrosis of a subchondral bone area with subsequent formation of an osteochondral fragment and its subsequent migration into the joint cavity.

Over the 8 years of our practice, we have seen patients with different stages of OCP of the humeral trochlea. Understanding all the stages of the disease, at which OCP can be recognized by characteristic radiographic manifestations and symptoms (*osteochondrosis manifesta*), it was not difficult for us to distinguish one stage from another. Radiographs should always be compared with an asymptomatic elbow, since the appearance of the trochlea anatomy varies from person to person.

We do not agree with the scheme of changes in the elbow joint in Hegemann's disease proposed by Schumacher et al. in 1981 (Fig.7). We offer our own scheme of changes in OCP of the humeral trochlea (Fig.8).

Stage 4: Regeneration and enlargement of the ossification center;

Stage 5: Final stage (complete or partial restoration).

Stages of development of osteochondropathy of the humerus trochlea
[by Umarov A.M. 2018]

Pathogenesis and etiology of osteochondropathy of the humerus trochlea
[by Umarov A.M. 2023]

The term “*osteochondrosis*” proposed by Hegemann H. and Western specialists cannot be applied for this disease. Because “*osteochondrosis*” is a chronic degenerative, irreversible disease of hyaline cartilage, which is a regressive process, both for to natural, age-related reasons, and after inflammatory, post-traumatic changes. The cause of osteochondrosis: hyaline cartilage loses moisture. Due to dehydration, micro-cracks, tears (ruptures), delamination and cracking of the fibers of the latter occur, with subsequent proliferation of fibrous tissue, with transformation into bone tissue. This leads to the loss of the main quality of cartilage: turgor (elasticity) and sliding. As a result, due to atrophy, the thickness of hyaline (articular) cartilage gradually decreases and, accordingly, the height of the joint gap decreases to a thread-like size, and the articular surfaces converge. The contours of the surfaces become deformed and uneven. The zones of subchondral sclerosis become compaction and thickened. At the same time, the opposing edges are horizontally extended in the form of sclerosis beak-shaped growths (osteophytes). The composition and viscosity of the synovial fluid (effusion) also change, which leads to a loss of moisture by the cartilage.

Cartilage does not contain blood vessels, nerves or lymphatic systems, and *nutrients diffuse into it through the matrix from the synovial fluid* – that is, it is the synovial fluid, not the blood, that nourishes the cartilage, but the synovial fluid. Therefore, in the case of OCP, we will not see changes in the hyaline articular cartilage on histological sections and in MRI studies. And since cartilage does not trochlea X-rays, we see changes occurring only in the subchondral bone part of the articular surface.

Osteochondropathy is a chronic, but regenerative, reversible disease (with timely detection and proper treatment is 80-88%). Therefore, stage V is called - *reparation*. Because it occurs more often in childhood, adolescence (teenagers) and young adulthood with a high degree of tissue regeneration. Also the process occurs

in middle-aged (30-40 years) people with relatively preserved tissue regeneration. The exception is the elderly (55-65 years old) with slowed or absent regeneration.

In connection with the above-stated well-known facts, it is correct to call this group of diseases not *osteochondropathy* (from Latin: *osteon* - bone, *chondros* - cartilage, *pathos* - suffering), but *subchondral osteopathy*. In this article, we propose to make additions to the generally accepted classification of OCP based on newly discovered data. As of 2024, ICD-X/10(91-98) distinguishes four groups of osteochondropathy.

Classification of osteochondropathy by process localization
[ICD-X/10(91-98)]

- I. Osteochondropathies of the epiphyseal ends of tubular bones.
- II. Osteochondropathies of short spongy bones.
- III. Osteochondropathies of the apophyses.
- IV. Partial (wedge-shaped) osteochondropathy of articular surfaces (osteochondritis dissecans).

1) We propose to amend the international classification ICD-X/10(91-98) and create group V: "Osteochondropathies of large (flat) spongy bones", which do not fit into any of the groups (Pearson's disease, M. van Neck and Odelberg disease, Hössler's disease, Cleaves-2 disease).

2) We also propose our own classification of osteochondropathy by pathogenesis and etiology.

Classification of ACH by pathogenesis and etiology
[according to Umarov A.M. 2023]

I. Factors leading to the zone of avascular necrosis.

1. External influence:

- long-term immobilization of joints in a plaster cast for more than 1 month.
- long-term lying in one position, on one side.
- long-term compression with diapers, ropes, lassos, passing main or subcutaneous vessels.
- long-term mechanical, monotonous load on the epiphysis/apophysis of the bone.
- trauma, fracture.
- long-term use of corticosteroids
- ionizing radiation
- cytotoxic agents

2. Internal effects:

- genotypic predisposition to impaired mineralization in the subchondral layer (SLE, sickle cell anemia, hyper coagulation, hemoglobinopathy, oxidative stress).
- phenotypic predisposition to impaired mineralization in the subchondral layer.
- dysplasia/hypoplasia of the epiphysis/apophysis of the bone.
- infectious effects (COVID, etc.) with the formation of thrombosis in the peripheral capillaries of the subchondral bone layer.
- impaired angiogenesis.

II. By the nature of the injury.

- primary micro trauma (micro compression) of the subchondral bone layer, as a result of a single or prolonged mechanical impact.
- secondary, one-stage trauma leading to a compression fracture or fragmentation of the necrotic area.

Etiology of the osteochondropathy

We also believe that the etiology of OCP is a special expressiveness of the individual (a complex relationship between the phenotype at the level of human genes [25,28,32,46,49,90] and its observed characteristics). It manifests itself in a violation of mineralization and the ratio of phosphorus-calcium metabolism in the subchondral part of the bone [31]. Therefore, OCP occurs in only 1-1.5% of patients among all diseases of the bone and joint system. OCP is based on a vascular-dystrophic process and a violation of the local sympathetic innervation of the vessels of the subchondral parts of the epiphyses (apophyses) of the bones in places of increased mechanical load. This leads to the formation of an *avascular zone*, resulting in aseptic osteonecrosis of this area. Trauma provokes an area of discharged bone tissue, which does not bother the patient at rest. There is also an opinion that the disease can develop as a result of infection or hereditary predisposition [25,28,29,32,46,49,90].

We believe that in such patients, as a result of the weakness of the trabecular-trabecular structure [31], under mechanical load, a primary micro trauma occurs, which patients often do not remember, there is micro compression of a certain spongy area of bone tissue in the subchondral zone and compression of the feeding vessels (mechanical obstruction of blood flow, thrombotic occlusion of vessels, extravascular compression). Due to this, an *internal avascular zone* occurs, depending on the area of compression of the spongy part, leading to the formation of a hidden (latent) zone of aseptic

necrosis, which is *invisible* on radiographs. This process can also occur with *external compression* of blood vessels during tight swaddling, tying children (especially 1 year of life) in cradles, cribs, beshikes; long lying in one position; in long-term wearing of plaster casts-pants (occurs in Legg-Calve-Perthes disease). In these cases, an avascular zone occurs due to external influence.

Secondary trauma provokes a hidden zone of aseptic necrosis and triggers all stages of development of OCP (Fig. 10-F, 12-H).

In the *first X-ray stage*, there is local loosening, blurring of contours and turbidity of the subchondral articular surface of the medial edge of the humeral trochlea (Fig. 13, 14). Many radiologists, orthopedists and endocrinologists interpret this as rheumatoid arthritis or its erosive form. But this tells us that in place of the avascular zone, a radiologically **visible zone** of aseptic necrosis has arisen in the subchondral layer. Due to a one-time or long-term mechanical load, compression of this local, softened area of the bone occurs. At this stage, the first clinical signs of pain syndrome appear, due to the fact that softened spongy bone tissue has formed under the dome of the hyaline cartilage, signs of primary intraosseous edema around the necrosis zone. Due to the disruption of the architectonics, in the form of poor mechanical support between the hyaline cartilage and the subchondral spongy part of the bone, the hyaline cartilage begins to "spring" with any physical activity and pressure on it. Which, in combination with intraosseous edema, causes irritation of the peripheral nerve endings and manifests itself as pain syndrome. At rest, pain, as a rule, does not appear.

The second stage manifests itself in all forms of OCP (including in the humeral trochlea) in the form of a compacted, thickened strip of necrosis of the subchondral articular surface (Fig. 12-C), due to compression. The contours of the subchondral articular surface of the bone are deformed, flattened, become uneven, unclear, and the bone structure in the affected area is compacted, becomes heterogeneous-granular (necrotic masses). The joint space in any joint, including the elbow joint (between the humeral trochlea and ulna) begins to expand. Due to compensatory thickening of the hyaline cartilage and due to compensatory production of effusion (additional synovial fluid), which allows the articular surfaces to be moved apart from each other in order to reduce pain.

In the *third stage*, a necrotic core begins to be traced on radiographs inside the humeral block (Fig. 15, 18). All these changes end either with fragmentation of this sequestrum-like core into several small fragments with their subsequent resorption in the subchondral zone (Fig. 16, 17), or as a result of a compression fracture, a dense sequestrum with a clear but uneven contour is formed. Due to secondary trauma, a local fracture of the hyaline cartilage occurs above the necrosis area (Fig. 10-F, 12-H), and the sequestrum separates into the elbow joint cavity, and then either resorbs or becomes covered with its own hyaline cartilage (Fig. 18), and becomes a free body. Rarely, a characteristic symptom of "**joint mouse**" appears in the joint cavity,

which (as in the knee joint) sometimes blocks movement in the elbow joint (2 cases out of 12 observed patients), which leads to a short-term limitation of flexion-extension functions. This is confirmed by MRI [32,43,46,78] (Fig. 9), histologically [31,32,49,52,65,82,83,88] (Fig. 11), arthroscopically during its surgical removal, both in the elbow and knee

joints [2,12,16,39,48,77,81,87]. The joint space remains widened. The hyaline cartilage is gradually restored in the fracture area and takes the external form of the subchondral bone structure (Fig. 12-J and 12-K).

Fig. 9

Fig. 9. The arrow indicates the sequestration fragment along the medial surface of the femur in Koenig-I disease. A zone of intraosseous edema can be traced around the sequestrum [46].

With timely detection of this disease and proper treatment, refusal of physical loads on the joint, it is possible to prevent the formation of a free bone body (sequestrum) conservatively. The contours of the subchondral articular surface of the humeral block are restored faster, become clear and even. The joint space returns to its normal size or narrows. Limitations of flexion-extension functions and external angular deformation in the elbow joint after treatment are not observed in 92-95% (*stage five*) (Fig. 19). When the previous shape of the subchondral articular surface is restored, the articular hyaline cartilage is also restored.

Antirheumatoid treatment with hormone therapy prescribed to patients with osteochondropathy, instead of improving, leads to deterioration and the formation of arthritis (arthrosis).

We have noticed that when orthopedists considered this to be post-traumatic arthritis or sprain and applied a gypsum bandage to the elbow joint for a period

of one month, completely immobilizing the joint, the bone structure was restored, which was confirmed on radiographs (Fig. 19, 20), the pain stopped and the patients recovered.

Below is a diagram of changes in the epiphyseal-articular cartilage in OD (Fig. 10), proposed by McCoy FV et al. in 2013. We consider this diagram to be incomplete. Therefore, we presented our version of changes in the epiphyseal-articular cartilage in OD, taking into account new data (Fig. 12).

Scheme of aseptic necrosis development and its transformation during treatment and during trauma

(Diagrams and microphotographs demonstrating the pathogenesis of osteochondropathy in animals)

Fig. 10
(by McCoy FV, Tóth F, Dolvik NI, Ekman S, Ellerman JM)

Explanation of Fig. 10.

Fig. 11
(by Tóth F, Carlson CS)

Figs. 1-A through 1-J Diagrams and photomicrographs demonstrating the pathogenesis of osteochondrosis in animals (**Figs. 1-A through 1-G**) and OCD in human pediatric cadavers (**Figs. 1-H, 1-I, and 1-J**). **Fig. 1-A** Normal endochondral ossification. **Fig. 1-B** Development of osteochondrosis latens because of failure of the cartilage canal blood supply, resulting in epiphyseal cartilage necrosis. **Fig. 1-C** Osteochondrosis manifesta lesion develops as a delay in the progression of the ossification front. **Figs. 1-D and 1-E** Healing of an osteochondrosis manifesta lesion by incorporation into subchondral bone. **Figs. 1-F and 1-G** Development of an OCD lesion as a result of trauma, causing collapse of articular cartilage overlying areas of necrotic epiphyseal cartilage.

Fig. 1-H Hematoxylin and eosin staining of articular and epiphyseal cartilage from the central aspect of the medial femoral condyle from a 4-year-old female donor containing an osteochondrosis latens lesion. Arrowheads demarcate necrotic epiphyseal cartilage.

Right: High-magnification image demonstrates cartilage canal containing multiple degenerate vessels. **Fig. 1-I** Hematoxylin and eosin staining of articular and epiphyseal cartilage from the central aspect of the medial femoral condyle from a 9-year-old male donor containing an osteochondrosis manifesta lesion. **Right:** High-magnification image demonstrates necrotic epiphyseal cartilage partially surrounded by bone. **Fig. 1-J** Hematoxylin and eosin staining of articular and epiphyseal cartilage from the central aspect of the lateral femoral condyle from a 4-year-old female donor containing a healing osteochondrosis manifesta lesion. Arrow points to a degenerate cartilage canal. **Right:** High-magnification image demonstrates necrotic epiphyseal cartilage completely surrounded by bone.

Note: Figures taken from: (21[65]:1638-47; 100[83]:2132-39; 44[90]:429-48; 28[49]:17-32).

Scheme of aseptic necrosis development and its transformation during treatment and during trauma

[modified according to Umarov A.M. 2023e.]

Fig. 12

Explanations for Fig. 12

A - Normal subchondral ossification. **B** - Latent development of OCP due to local disruption of blood supply to the cartilaginous canal, resulting in aseptic necrosis of the epiphyseal cartilage (arrow). **C** and **D** - Visible zone of aseptic necrosis, where **C** is in the form of a necrotic plate, and **D** is in the form of a necrotic focus. **E** and **G** - The processes of healing of OCP and resorption of the necrotic focus. **F** - The process of migration of the necrotic focus, pushing away and deforming the hyaline cartilage along the forward. **H** - Compression fracture of a softened local area of aseptic necrosis and hyaline cartilage. **I** and **J** - Sequestration of the sequestrum with the formation of a free fragment covered with its own hyaline cartilage. At the site of separation, a deformation depression is formed with gradual regeneration of the shape of the hyaline cartilage.

K - Fragmentation of the sequestrum with subsequent resorption and regeneration of the hyaline cartilage.

Note: Based on figures from: (21[65]:1638-47; 100[83]:2132-39), modified and supplemented in 2023.

Below we have selected and presented radiographs from our own archives of both adolescent boys and adults that best characterize radiologically a new type of OCP in the elbow joint. The radiographs are (mostly) presented only in the forward-anterior projection, because in the lateral projection, the affected area is poorly differentiated.

The left elbow joint

Fig. 13

Patient D. 11 years. (in 2018y.)

Fig. 13. The patient D. (age 11 years) addressed in 2018 about the pain in the right elbow joint, also after playing tennis. Direct-anterior radiography was performed on X-ray machine EDR-750 (Hungary) 1979: time 0.16 s, voltage 50 keV, current 200 mA, equivalent dose 0.04 mSv. The contours of the left humerus trochlea are uneven, indistinct. The formation of aseptic necrosis zone is well traced (indicated by an arrow).

The articular gap between the humerus and ulna is widened in the joint. There is a weakly expressed external angular deformity in the left elbow joint (cubitus valgus = 12°/168°). Cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is intact.

The following **conclusion** was made: “Osteochondropathy of the medial trochlea of the left humerus in the stage of aseptic necrosis”.

The right elbow joint

Fig. 14

Patient K. 10 years. (in 2017y)

Fig. 14. Patient K. (age 10 years) addressed in 2017 about the pain in the right elbow joint after playing tennis. Direct-anterior radiograph was performed on X-ray machine EDR-750 (Hungary) 1979: time 0.16 s, voltage 50 keV, current 200 mA, equivalent dose 0.08 mSv. The contours of the humerus trochlea are uneven, not clear, not sharp. The lower surface of the trochlea is clearly traceable forming necrotized nucleus. The articular gap between the humerus and ulna is widened. An external angular deformity in the right

Fig. 15

The same patient K., in 2019y.

elbow joint (cubitus valgus = 15°/165°) is noted. Cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is intact.

The following **conclusion** was made: “Osteochondropathy of the right humerus trochlea in the stage of radiologic turbidity and aseptic necrosis”.

Fig. 15. Patient K. re-applied in 2019 after 2 years (age 12 years) after appropriate treatment. A control radiography of the right elbow joint was scheduled, performed on the X-ray device “Baccara” (France) 2015: time 0.10 s, voltage 45 keV, current strength 200 mA,

equivalent dose 0.04 mSv. On the direct-anterior radiograph the presence of a free sequestrum (bone fragment) in the area of the medial edge of the humerus trochlea with uneven, but with clear and sharp contours, with a dense structure is determined. The articular gap between the humerus trochlea and ulna in the joint returned to the original size. No restrictions of flexion-extension functions or external angular deformity in the

right elbow joint were observed in the patient after treatment (cubitus rectus). Cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is not disturbed.

The following **conclusion** was made: “Osteochondropathy of the right humerus trochlea in the fragmentation stage with the formation of free bone sequestrums (joint «mouse»).

The left elbow joint

Fig. 16

Teenager J. 11 years old (in 2022).

Fig. 16. Patient J. (age 11 years) came in the summer of 2022 for pain in the left elbow joint after playing table tennis. On the performed direct-anterior radiograph on the X-ray apparatus “Baccara” (France) 2015: time 0.10 s, voltage 45 keV, current strength 200 mA, equivalent dose 0.04 mSv the presence of 2 different-sized free sequestrations (bone fragments) in the area of the humerus trochlea with uneven, clear and sharp contours, with a less dense structure is determined. The

articular gap between the humerus and ulna was widened. The patient had flexion-extension limitations in the elbow joint and external angular deformity in the elbow joint (cubitus varus = 26°/154°). Cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is not disturbed.

The following **conclusion** was made: “Osteochondropathy of the left humerus trochlea in the fragmentation stage with the formation of 2 bone sequestrums (joint «mouse») in the joint cavity.

*The left elbow joint
(in 2 projections)*

Fig. 17

Boy A. 11 years old (in 2021).

Fig. 17. Patient A. (11 years old) applied in 2021 for pain in the left elbow joint after a painful attack on the elbow joint during judo wrestling. X-rays in 2 projections on X-ray apparatus “Baccara” (France) 2015

were performed: time 0,10 s, voltage 45 keV, current strength 200 mA, equivalent dose 0,04 mSv. The contours of the humerus trochlea are uneven, clear, sharp. Fragmented, necrotized, small nuclei located in the

joint cavity are traced on the lower surface of the trochlea. The articular gap between the humeral trochlea and ulna is widened. There is no external angular deformity in the right elbow joint (cubitus rectus). Cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is not disturbed.

The following **conclusion** was made: “Osteochondropathy of the left humerus trochlea in the stage of multiple fragmentation”.

The right elbow joint

Fig. 18

Boy R. 12 years old (in 2019).

Figure 18: Patient R. (age 12 years) came in 2019 for pain in the right elbow joint after playing volleyball. A direct-anterior radiograph was performed on a 1979 EDR-750 (Hungary) X-ray machine: time 0.16s, voltage 50 keV, current 200mA, equivalent dose 0.06mSv. The contours of the humerus trochlea are oblique to the outside, uneven, indistinct, not sharp. A separated necrotized large nucleus into the joint cavity can be traced along the lower surface of the trochlea. The articular

gap between the trochlea of the humerus and ulna is widened. A slight external angular deformity in the right elbow joint (cubitus varus = 24o/156o) is noted. Cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus is intact.

The following **conclusion** was made: “Osteochondropathy of the right humerus trochlea in the stage of fragmentation with sequestrum formation (joint “mouse”).

The final stages of osteochondropathy

Dissecans osteochondritis
Right elbow joint
Fig. 19

The man is 28 years old.

Panner's disease-2
Left elbow joint
Fig. 20

The man is 52 years old.

Fig. 19. A man T.S. (28 years old) came in 2017. with complaints of pain and limitation of flexor-extensor functions in the right elbow joint after digging up beds in the garden. From anamnesis: in childhood, he was treated for a long time for sudden pain in this

joint. A direct-anterior radiograph was performed on the «Baccara» X-ray machine (France) 2015: time 0.10s, voltage 45keV, current 200mA, equivalent dose 0.04 mSv. The contours of the humerus trochlea have been relatively restored to their previous size, clear,

wavy. The articular gap between the humerus trochlea and the bones of the forearm is narrowed to 1-1.5mm. There is no angular deformation in the right elbow joint (cubitus rectus). There is a flattening of the capitulum (cephalic eminence) of the humerus.

The **conclusion** was made: "Osteochondropathy of the trochlea of the right humerus in arthrosis stage II-III degree".

Fig. 20. The man T.K. (52) came in 2017. with complaints of pain and limitation of flexor-extensor functions in the left elbow joint. From anamnesis: as a child, he was treated for pain in this joint for a long time. In 1975, he was diagnosed with rheumatoid arthritis of the left elbow joint. I was receiving hormone therapy. I felt the improvement only after applying a gypsum bandage for a period of 1 month. A direct-anterior radiograph was performed on an EDR-750 X-ray machine (Hungary) 1979: time 0.16s, voltage 50keV, current 200mA, equivalent dose 0.08mSv. The contours of the humerus trochlea are smooth, clear, and not deformed. The heterogeneous density of the bone structure and the uneven contours of the cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the humerus are noted. The articular gap between the humerus trochlea and the bones of the forearm is narrowed to 1.5 mm. There is an external angular deformation in the joint (cubitus varus = 25°/155°).

The **conclusion** was made: "Osteochondropathy of the cephalic eminence (capitulum) of the left humerus (Panner's disease-2) in the arthrosis stage of the II degree".

Results and discussion

The authors of this work have studied and analyzed radiographs of various variants of osteochondropathies. Collecting scientific material from our own archive and comparing X-ray images from monographs and scientific publications, we came to the conclusion that changes in the humerus trochlea in the elbow joint are a new type of osteochondropathy, since all X-ray signs corresponded to the classical form of osteochondropathy with all radiological stages. Recall that these include:

Stage I – radiological turbidity or stage of aseptic necrosis.

Stage II – impression (compression).

Stage III – fragmentation (fragmentation).

Stage IV – repair (restoration) 92-95%.

Stage V is osteoarthritis (osteoarthrosis) (5-8%). It occurs (on average) after 1.5-2 years, with improper or not timely treatment. The result: ossification of the zone of aseptic necrosis (secondary osteosclerosis), with the formation of gross deformation of the contours and shape of the epiphysis or apophysis (beak-like growths) - osteoarthritis (osteocondrosis), which leads to partial contractures and external angular deformation in the joint. This will lead to disability and surgical intervention with the development of pronounced deformities or the presence of intra-articular bodies leading to joint trochlea.

Conclusions:

Early and correct X-ray diagnosis of any type of osteochondropathy, including osteochondropathy identified by us (osteochondritis of the epiphysis of the humerus trochlea in the elbow joint), with an understanding of the radiological and clinical picture of the disease, will lead to early detection, proper treatment and recovery, without complications or limitations of flexor-extensor functions. This will prevent surgery or treatment for other diseases (arthritis, arthrosis) with the use of hormone therapy, which is directly contraindicated in osteochondropathy. But if this pathology is not detected and treated in a timely manner, then the patient will develop osteoarthritis and angular deformity in the joint. This will result in surgery or disability. We claim that this is a new type of osteochondropathy. Based on the X-ray picture and all stages of development that bone and articular cartilage undergo, this pathology should be included in the IV group of partial (wedge-shaped) osteochondropathies of articular surfaces under the term "Subepiphyseal osteochondropathy of the humerus trochlea" (Osteochondritis dissecans) according to the international classification of ICD-X/10(91-98).

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